

Fatigue improvement of welded cover-plates using High Frequency Mechanical Impact Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Many existing steel and composite bridges in Sweden need strengthening and upgrading in order to meet demands on higher axle loads. One method that is widely used to increase the bending resistance of beams is to add cover-plates. The solution adopted today is to bolt the plates to the existing structure to avoid welding and the accompanied reduction in fatigue strength brought by this detail which has very low fatigue strength. The use of bolted connections with many holes drilled on site and fitted bolts is very costly. Therefore, a research program has been initiated to study the possibility of using High-Frequency Mechanical Impact (HFMI) treatment to enhance the fatigue strength of the ends of welded cover-plates. This paper reports the results from fatigue tests done on beams with welded cover-plates, with and without HFMI-treatment. The beams and cover plates were made of S355 steel, and all tests were conducted with an R-ratio of 0.1. The results from preliminary numerical analysis to evaluate the risk for root cracking in these details are also reported. The results from testing show that HFMI-treatment can produce an improvement in fatigue strength of welded cover-plates with more than four detail categories. No root cracking was observed in any of the tested beams.

Keywords: Fatigue, Cover-plate, HFMI, Bridges, Strengthening

1 INTRODUCTION

The Swedish Transport Administration (Trafikverket) manages a large number of existing bridges that need to be strengthened and upgraded to meet current and future requirement on heavier vehicles and more intensive traffic. In particular, upgrading large parts of the Swedish road network to BK4 (allowing vehicles with gross weight of 74 tonnes) puts many bridges in this category. One method of strengthening existing steel and composite bridges which is widely used today is to increase members section modulus by attaching steel cover-plates. Bolted connections are usually used to connect the cover -plates to the existing members to avoid the considerably low fatigue strength that is associated with welded cover-plate ends (i.e. detail category 36-56 according to EN 1993-1-9). In order to ensure full load transfer between the existing member and the cover-plates the practice is to use fitted bolts which in turn required the cover-plate and the part to be strengthened (beam flange, for example) to be drilled on site in the same operation, see *Fig. 1*. This makes this – otherwise very effective - strengthening method rather cumbersome and expensive. The risk of crevice corrosion of the resulting detail is another drawback that would be excluded if welded cover-plates could be used. This has motivated an investigation of the feasibility of using welded cover-plates along with High Frequency Mechanical Impact treatment of the critical plate ends to enhance the detail fatigue performance.

The efficiency of HFMI-treatment has been demonstrated in numerous previous studies. The bulk of experimental tests has however been conducted on the three most common and simple welded details, namely: transverse butt welds, welded transverse and welded longitudinal attachments. Therefore, the upcoming updates of EN 1993-1-9 covers only these three types of welded details with respect to HFMI-treatment (1).

Fig. 1. Example of beam cover-plate prepared for bolting to an existing bridge girder.

The earliest fatigue tests reported on the fatigue performance of HFMI-treated cover-plate details in beams were conducted by Roy and Fisher in 2006 (2). Here, 18 hot-rolled beams (W690x192) were equipped with 25 mm welded cover-plates in the configuration shown in *Fig. 2*. The cover-plates in type CP1 and CP3, which are of interest here, were welded around the cover-plate ends, while specimens with ends of type CP2 were provided with longitudinal welds only. Specimens CP1 had transverse fillet welds (i.e. at the end of the cover-plate) with a weld leg length of 13 mm, while CP2 were equipped with 25 mm fillet welds (i.e. weld leg equal to half and full cover-plate thickness respectively). All tests with detail types CP1 failed with cracks initiating from weld toe. Beams with CP3 developed fatigue cracking from weld toe when tested at high stress ratio but were reported as run-out otherwise. One specimen had fatigue crack starting from a lack of fusion defect in weld root. Roy and Fisher tests showed that the fatigue strength of cover-plate details can be improved via HFMI-treatment and that this improvement is higher when bigger transverse fillet welds are employed (type CP3).

A second test series with identical set-up to that used by Roy and Fisher, was conducted by Hui et al (3). Here, however, all transverse welds at the ends of cover-plates had leg length equal to half the cover-plate thickness (i.e. Type CP1 in Roy and Fisher tests). Fourteen beams were tested, 10 with HFMI-treated details and 4 as-welded. Of the 20 cover-plate ends that were HFMI-treated, 12 were reported to have failed from weld root and only 3 ends had cracks initiated from weld toe. Therefore, Hui et al tests cannot be used to evaluate the fatigue strength enhancement that can be achieved by HFMI on cover-plate end details.

Fig. 2. Test setup used by Roy and Fisher (2) with the three different types of cover-plate end welds.

In addition to the aforementioned beam tests, fatigue tests of plates in tension, e.g. by Leitner and Stoschka (4) or bending, such as those reported by Vilhauer et al (5) have also been performed to evaluate the fatigue strength improvement obtained by HFMI-treatment. Such tests, however, while very valuable for estimating the fatigue strength improvement that can be achieved by HFMI-treatment in general, do not represent the severity of notch effect and the local stresses that are present in details with welded cover-plates in beams loaded in bending.

2 DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

Previous fatigue tests on beams with welded cover-plates provided little evidence on the improvement of fatigue strength that can be brought to these details by HFMI-treatment. Most tests either failed from the weld root or were reported as run-out. In addition, it was early recognised that the test setup used by Roy and Fisher (2006) and by Hui et al (2018) – i.e. placing the cover-plate at the support side – results in a stress state at the end of the cover-plate which differs from that obtained when the cover-plate is placed in beam mid-span. Therefore, beam tests with the setup shown in Fig 7 was chosen for the fatigue tests presented in this paper. Hot-rolled HEA200 beams are used, provided with 14 mm thick cover-plate (measured thickness 14,7 mm).

Prior to fatigue testing, FE-models employing the Effective Notch Stress method were constructed to analyse the expected fatigue performance of the test beams. In particular, the risk for root cracking after HFMI-treatment of the critical welds at the ends of the cover-plates needed to be assessed. Root cracking should be avoided if the full potential of HFMI-treatment of the weld toe is to be utilized. It was anticipated that the size of the transversal welds at the ends of the cover-plates has a pronounced effect on the local stress at the root side of the welds. Therefore, two cases are investigated with weld throat thicknesses of 5 and 10 mm. These correspond to weld leg length equal to half respectively full cover-plate thickness as was used by Roy and Fisher (2).

The results in terms of effective notch stress at the transverse weld toe and root at the end of the cover-plates are shown in Fig. 4. Values are given per 1 MPa nominal bending stress in the flange of the tested beams at the cover-plate termination.

Fig. 4. Effective Notch Stress (maximum principal) in weld toe and weld root for cover-plates with transverse welds with 5- and 10-mm throat thickness. Values given for 1 MPa nominal bending stress in beam flange at cover-plate end.

In the as-welded condition, both toe cracking and root cracking are to be related to detail category 225 MPa in the ENS-system with the principal stress (6). It is apparent that toe cracking governs irrespective of weld size. The results show that a bigger transverse weld size results in reduction of stress concentration both at weld toe and – more profoundly so – at weld root.

For HFMI-treated details, the situation is different, however. While detail category 225 is still valid for the weld root, the fatigue strength of the HFMI-treated toe is increased to 360 MPa (for steel S355) according to the IIW recommendations (6). In addition, fatigue of the HFMI-treated weld toe follows an S-N curve with a slope of 5, while the root side still obeys a slope of 3. This means that whether toe or root cracking will govern for any given case will depend on the stress range. This is illustrated in Fig. 5 where the number of cycles to failure at the cover-plate termination of the HEA200 beam is plotted against the nominal bending stress range in beam flange at the end of the cover-plate, for the two fillet weld sizes shown in Fig. 4. These results indicate that, even with bigger welds, root cracking may be the governing failure modes if the weld toe fatigue strength is increased substantially due to HFMI-treatment. It should be pointed out, however, that this “theoretical exercise” is only indicative of the influence of throat thickness of the transverse welds. In real connections, factors such as weld penetration, weld residual stresses and weld quality at the root side of the fillet weld will all influence the risk for root cracking.

Fig. 5. The stress range at which fatigue failure mode is transferred from toe to root cracking in HFMI-treated cover-plate details with transverse welds having 5- and 10-mm throat thickness.

3 TEST SPECIMEN PRODUCTION AND TESTING PROCEEDURE

Test specimens were made of 3,0 m long HEA200 beams loaded in 3-point bending with a span of 2,5 m. Cover plates – 1000x120x14 mm were welded on the tension flange (the measured nominal thickness of the cover-plate was 14,7 mm). Welding of the specimens was preceded with pre-trials on lap joints with similar thicknesses. The goal was to achieve weld throat thickness of 7 mm for the transverse welds (and some 120 mm of the longitudinal welds) at the ends of the cover-plate, see *Fig 6 and 7*. This required three passes of welds, one root pass and two parallel fill passes. All welding was made with spray arc using ESAB Autrod 12.51 1,2mm solid wire and Mison 18 shielding gas at 20l/min. Four tack welds (50mm in length placed 100mm from the corners) were used to fix each cover-plate prior to welding. These tack welds were grinded in the start and stop part before the final welding to avoid lack of fusion. The weld was made continuous around the corners of the cover-plates with the stop-start points located some 120 mm from the critical cover-plate ends, see *Fig 6*. These stop-start points were TIG-remelted according to the recommendations in IIW XIII-1815-00 (9) to reduce the risk for crack initiation from these locations, see *Fig. 7*.

Fig. 6. Pre-trials and final welding of cover-plate ends with reinforced welds.

Four of the beams served as reference and were tested in the as-welded condition. The cover-plate ends in another eight beams were HFMI-treated. The HFMI-treatment covered the transverse ends and ca 200 mm of the longitudinal welds on each side of the cover-plate ends, thus even the TIG-remelted stop-start points close to cover-plate ends. The HFMI-treatment was performed with a HiFit device using a 3 mm diameter pin. The stop-start locations were treated with a pin having a 10 mm diameter.

Each beam was equipped with 4 strain gauges, two on each end of the cover plate located on the flange edges, see *Fig 7*. In addition to measuring the bending strains in the flange at these locations, these strain gauges were used to detect fatigue cracking in beam flange at the ends of the cover-plate (i.e. by monitoring the change in strain during fatigue testing).

In total, 12 beams were tested, four in as welded condition and eight post-weld treated with HFMI. All tests were conducted with an R-ratio of 0,1 and the loading frequency was 7 Hz.

Fig. 7. Test set-up and detailing of cover-plate ends.

4 TEST RESULTS

All beams – as-welded and HFMI-treated – failed due to fatigue cracking along weld toe at either end of the cover-plate. Fig. 8 shows the cracks in specimens C03 (as-welded) and C06 (HFMI-treated). The test results are summarized in Table 1. The number of cycles to failure (N_{failure}) refers to a crack that had propagated through the thickness of the beam flange. Typically, at this stage, the crack length is approximately half a flange width long (along weld toe).

Fig. 8. Fatigue cracks in beams with as-welded (top) and HFMI-treated (bottom) cover-plates.

Table 1. Fatigue test results

Beam no.	Type	P_{\min} [kN]	P_{\max} [kN]	$\Delta\sigma$ [MPa]	N_{failure}
C01	AW	7,78	77,8	67,5	1 299 000
C02	AW	7,78	77,8	67,5	1 139 500
C03	AW	7,78	77,8	67,5	1 320 000
C04	AW	7,78	77,8	67,5	1 489 775
C05	HFMI	11	111	96,4	3 053 788
C06-1	HFMI	11	111	96,4	runout
C06-2	HFMI	13,3	133	115,4	1 685 373
C07	HFMI	13,3	133	115,4	758 672
C08	HFMI	13,3	133	115,4	540 972
C09	HFMI	12,2	122	105,8	949 641
C10	HFMI	12,2	122	105,8	1 850 000
C11	HFMI	12,2	122	105,8	1 480 000
C12	HFMI	12,2	122	105,8	1 001 099

All test results are also plotted in *Fig. 9*. The number of tests in as-welded condition is very limited and doesn't allow for a statistical evaluation of the detail category. These tests are shown in relation to detail category 50 which is relevant according to EN 1993-1-9 (7).

For the eight beams where the end of the cover-plates were HFMI-treated, statistical evaluation of test results was made following Drebenstedt and Euler (8). Enforcing a slope of 5, which is assigned to HFMI-treated details in various standards, a detail category (95% fractile) of 81,4 MPa is obtained with a standard deviation of 0.174. The closest detail category in EN 1993-1-9 is 80 MPa. If detail category 50 is adopted for the as-welded details, then the results suggest that HFMI-treatment resulted in an increase of fatigue strength with 4 detail categories, which is one step less than what is stipulated in the IIW-recommendations for steels with yield strength between 355 and 550 MPa.

Fig. 9. Test results for the as-welded and HFMI-treated beams.

5 SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

This paper presents the results from fatigue tests that have been conducted to evaluate the improvement of fatigue strength that can be achieved on welded cover-plate details using High Frequency Mechanical Impact (HFMI) treatment. Twelve HEA200 beams with 1000x120x14 mm² welded cover-plates were tested in 3-point bending. Four of the beams were in as welded condition while eight had the welds at cover-plate ends HFMI-treated.

The results show an improvement of fatigue strength of HFMI-treated welds with 4 detail categories compared to the as-welded details (detail category 80 vs 50 respectively). This demonstrates the efficiency of HFMI-treatment in improving the fatigue strength of the studied details.

All specimens developed cracks starting from weld toe. No root cracks were observed, despite the fact that Effective Notch Stress analysis suggests that root cracking would be the governing failure mode in almost all tests. This could be a consequence of the adopted welding procedure that might have contributed to compressive residual stress at the root of the fillet weld (i.e. the first root weld pass).

It should be pointed out here, that the results presented in this paper have been achieved on beams with similar dimensions, plate thicknesses and weld sizes. It is well known that the fatigue strength of welded cover-plates – at least in the as-welded condition – is dependent on the stiffness characteristics of beam flange and cover-plate, e.g. the ratio between cover-plate thickness and flange thickness. Therefore, more tests with other configurations and plate thickness ratios will be needed to validate and extend the applicability of the findings of this study.

Another important aspect that would need a broader study is the risk for root cracking in cover-plates with HFMI-treated ends. Dependent on several parameters including cover-plate thickness, weld size and detailing of cover-plate ends, root cracking might limit the benefit from HFMI-treatment. The risk for root cracking can be quantified analytically and verified experimentally. Several potential measures that can be taken to mitigate this risk are shown in *Fig. 10*. This should be a subject for future studies.

Fig. 10. Examples of cover-plate end detailing options that could mitigate the risk for root cracking.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work presented in this paper has been conducted within the research project “LifeExt2” (Vinnova 2021-01045). The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support provided by Vinnova and InfraSweden2030. The support provided by Ramboll and the Swedish Transport Administration is also acknowledged as well as the valuable contribution of HiFit who provided the HFMI-treatment.

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